

Study [SD]	Total Patient N: Patients receiving intervention (N); Patients receiving control treatment (N)	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Comparator (description)	Allocation procedure: Concealment attempts	Population: Broad outcome category/ies evaluated
Glass ionomer vs Composite resin					
Dermata 2008 [RCT] ¹	48: 25 Resin modified glass ionomer (Vitremmer); 23 Composite resin (Z250)	Resin modified glass ionomer cement (Vitremmer) [Class II restorations]: Placed under local analgesia/rubber-dam isolation. Cavities prepared with small cylindrical high-speed diamond bur, soft carious dentine removed using round, size 4, low-speed steel burs. Thin, 5 mm width, steel matrix band secured around approximal surface with wooden wedge suitable for primary molar restorations. Materials used according to manufacturer instructions. Primer applied 30s+light-cured 10s. Vitremmer powder+liquid dose manually mixed, placed in cavity with recommended application tip+light-cured 40s. Restoration trimmed+polished. Finishing gloss applied using microbrush, gently blown and cured 20s. Occlusion checked above. Dental staff: 6trained and calibrated 2nd/3rd yr postgraduate Paediatric Dentistry students. Trained: during Yr1 postgraduate studies+for appropriate cavity shape/sizes on natural extracted primary molars. Evaluated: 10 class II restorations on clinic patients before study start	Composite resin (Z250) [Class II restorations]: After etching enamel with 37% phosphoric acid gel for 30s, and dentine for 8s, thorough rinsing and careful drying for 15s conducted. Bonding agent (Adper Scotchbond XT, 3M ESPE, St.Paul, MN, USA) applied/light-cured for 10s. Z250 incrementally applied in 2 stages, with each layer light-cured for 20s. Trimming/polishing performed using conical Arkansas stone. After rubber-dam removal, occlusion checked and trimming repeated if needed	Allocation: Unrestricted computer-generated list of random numbers through clinic management patients to two restoration materials. Concealment: Clinicians: informed prior to placement of restoration by third person patient allocated material+all patients Class II cavities of primary teeth restored same material. Blinding six treatment providers not possible, (visual/protocol differences). Patients: No measures, but not informed re: material received (materials visually similar). 4 outcome assessors: blinded, may perceive group allocation, due to expertise. Data analyst blinded	Patient: OH
Gavic 2019 [RCT] ²	60: 3 treatment groups 1) 20 GIC (Ketac Molar); 2) 20 GIC (Ionofil Molar); 3) 20 Compomer (Twinkly Star)	Glass ionomer cement (2x types: Ketac Molar and Ionofil Molar) or compomer (1 type) [Class II preparations]: Incrementally filled with dental materials, according to manufacturer's instructions	NA	Allocation: Subjects randomly assigned 3 equal groups (20 each), according to restoration material. Concealment: NR	Patient: Genotoxicity
Composite resin					

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Hu 2021 [Retrospective observational - Nested case-control] ³	14,952: 4984 Patients with ADHD (3500 with restorations); 9968 No ADHD (6696 with restorations)	Composite resin: operative dentistry treatment	No composite restorations	NA	Patient: ADHD
Leybovich 2014 [RCT-1 arm relevant] ⁴	8 patients(24 sites): 12 sites treated subepithelial connective tissue graft; 12 sites Class V composite resin restoration	CRR: Sites treated by clinician. Protocol: Sites prepared conservatively, retraction cord (Ultrapak, Ultradent) utilized for advisualizeaequate submarginaltion and hemostasis. Matching composite shad chosen. Tooth restored, finished, and polished (TPH3 Micro composite,Dentsply Caulk)	CTG: Not relevant to review	NR	Patient: OH
Pettini 2015 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁵	40: 20 exposure; 20 control	Composite resin (Enamel-Plus-HFO (Micerium S.p.A., Avegno, Italy. (Microhybrid): Main components: bis-GMA, TEGDMA, UDMA resin 5.2% butandioldimethacrylate, 66.3 vol% strontium, aluminium, glass (silanized) 7.6 wt% siliciumoxide, 0.3 wt% pigments. Curing method: 40s photo-polymerization, 650mW/cm2 (bluephase)	No amalgam, no composite resin exposure	NA	Patient: Genotoxicity
Tadin 2014 [RCT] ⁶	30: 15 Kalore; 15 Vertise	Composite resin [Class V]: Kalore (nanohybrid composite): 18% Resin (UDMA, dimethacrylate co-monomers, DX-511 monomer)+82% Fillers (Strontium glass (400 nm), lanthanoid fluoride (100 nm), strontium glass (700 nm), fluoroaluminosilicate glass (700 nm), silicon dioxide (16 nm))+Self-ech adhesive system (G-bond). Class V preparations incrementally filled with dental composite materials, according to manufacturer's instructions, polymerized by Bluephase C8 curing unit (800 mW/cm2;	Composite resin [Class V]: Vertise flow (self-adhering flowable composite): 18-40% Resin (GPDM adhesive monomer, Kerr's optibond adhesion technology) +60-82% Fillers (Barium glass (0.7 µm), barium glass (1 µm), colloidal silica (10–40 nm), ytterbium fluoride (40 nm)). Class V preparations incrementally filled with dental composite materials, according to	Allocation: Randomly assigned numerically equal groups according to restoration material. Concealment: NR	Patient: Genotoxicity

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		Ivoclar Vivadent, Schaan, Liechtenstein) with soft-start mode of 40s	manufacturer's instructions, polymerized by Bluephase C8 curing unit(800 mW/cm2; Ivoclar Vivadent, Schaan, Liechtenstein), soft-start mode 40s		
Woods 2009 [RCT] ⁷	479 with porphyrin analyses available: 237 amalgam; 242 RBC. Restricted to 8-9yrs: 195 (88 Amalgam, 107 RBC)	Amalgam [See De Rouen 2006]	Composite resin [See De Rouen 2006]	See De Rouen 2006	Patient: Renal
Amalgam vs Composite resin (comparative)					

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Maserejian 2012 Dental composites and amalgam and physical health [Secondary analysis RCT] ⁹	474 included in analysis: Included in growth outcomes analysis: 238 Amalgam; 236 Composite	See Bellinger 2006	See Bellinger 2006	See Bellinger 2006	Patient: Anthromorphic, FH,
Bellinger 2006 [RCT] ⁹	534: 267Amalgam (262 received treatment)a, 267 Composite (263 received treatment)	Amalgam [restoration of min.2+ occlusal dental caries lesions]: Dispersed phase amalgam used to restore all posterior teeth with caries at baseline and to restore incident caries during 5yr trial	Resin composite material (white restoration): For both groups, composite material used to restore caries in front teeth+ stainless steel crowns used to restore primary teeth with extensive lesions that could not be restored using either assigned restorative material. Choices of dental materials/techniques standardized across sites+dentists. Both groups semi-annual dental examinations+additional visits to meet treatment needs	Allocation: Randomization stratified by geographic location and n. teeth with caries (2-4 vs 5 or more) using randomly permuted blocks within each of 4 strata (Boston, 2-4 caries, n=103; Boston, 5 caries, n=188; Maine, 2-4 caries, n=141; Maine, 5 caries, n=102). Concealment: Assignment made via telephone using software and encrypted files by New England Research Institutes personnel who not involved in data collection. Participants/ dentists could not be blinded to treatment assignment. Data outcome collectors+those analyzing specimens blinded to children's treatment assignment	Patient: AE, Allergy, Blood disorder, Cancer, CVD, Dermatological, Endocrine, Exposure, GI, GPH, MSK, Neurological, NeuroPsych, Psych, Renal, Resp, Sensory Disorder

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Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ¹⁰	59: 29 Amalgam; 30 Composite	Amalgam [See Bellinger 2006]	<p>Composite [See Bellinger 2006]. 3xclasses resin-composite materials: (i) Flowable composites [Preventive sealants+ PRR], (ii) Non-flowable standard bisGMA-based composite [Restoration permanent tooth caries], (iii) Non-flowable polyacid-modified UDMA-based composite (compomer) [Restoration of primary (deciduous) tooth caries]. Compomer more commonly used at study start given prevalence primary teeth caries, composite more frequently during follow-up, as new decay on permanent teeth occurred. Most compomer-filled primary teeth exfoliated by end of follow-up; only 4 children had compomer present at Year 5. At yr5, 58% children composites on permanent teeth, many placed post-baseline (surfaces newly placed, mean=1.9, SD=2.8). Exposure accumulated most for sealants during the study (surface-years, mean=28.1, SD=19.6), as these were routinely placed where clinically appropriate</p>	See Bellinger 2006	Patient: IF

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Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and psychosocial [Secondary analysis RCT] ¹¹	434 included in analysis: 217 Assigned any composite; 217 Assigned amalgam; 214 Received compomer, 220 Received composite, 216 Received amalgam	Amalgam [See Bellinger 2006]	Composite resin [See Bellinger 2006]	See Bellinger 2007	Patient: Behaviour, Psych,
Maserejian 2014 Dental sealants and flowable composite restorations [Secondary analysis RCT] ¹²	N children material placed during trial: 397 Sealant; 290 PRR	Flowable composite (sealant)-Ultraseal XT by Ultradent (South Jordan, Utah, USA) [Preventive sealing sound pits/fissures of posterior teeth]. Flowable composite- Revolution by Kerr (Orange, Calif., USA) PRRs[Shallow, incipient caries not extending into dentin]: Composite restoration materials used: Permanent teeth: Z100 by 3M ESPE (St. Paul, Minn., USA), Primary teeth: Dyract AP compomer by Dentsply Caulk (Milford, Del., USA). Sealants and PRRs were placed as needed regardless of assigned treatment group for restorations. Participants received comprehensive dental care semi-annually for 5yrs. Standard dental care: exams, cleaning, fluoride application, sealant placement+restorative treatment. Dental procedures and materials standardized across study sites, following manufacturer's instructions	NA	See Bellinger 2006	Patient: Anthromorphic, Behaviour, FH, NeuroPsych, Psych, SW

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Maserejian 2012 Dental composite restorations and neuropsychological [Secondary analysis RCT] ¹³	444 had yr5 outcome data, 409 yr4 outcome data. Compomer N [NR]; Composite N [NR]	Composite/Compomer resin: Permanent teeth: Aminifill composite (Z100, by 3M ESPE, St. Paul, Minn) containing bisGMA and TEGDMA for resin matrix, Primary teeth: (Dyract, by Dentsply Caulk, Milford, Del.) Compomer (polyacid-modified composites. 72% strontium-fluorosilicate-glass; contained urethane dimethacrylate and trimethacrylate resins. Composites used in amalgam arm of RCT (Bellinger 2006) to restore anterior tooth caries, per standard practice. Children had semiannual dental examinations and treatment visits as needed throughout 5yr follow-up. Dental procedures standardized across sites and clinicians	NA	See Bellinger 2006	Patient : NeuroPsych
Shenker 2008 [Secondary analysis RCT] ¹⁴	59: 29 Amalgam, 30 Composite	Amalgam [See Bellinger 2006]	Composite resin [See Bellinger 2006]	See Bellinger 2008	Patient: Exposure, IF
Bellinger 2007 [Dental amalgam restorations, neuroPsych function] [RCT] ¹⁵	534: 267 Amalgam; 267 Composite	Amalgam [See Bellinger 2006]	Composite resin [See Bellinger 2006]	See Bellinger 2009	Patient: NeuroPsych

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Bellinger 2008 [RCT] ¹⁶	534: 267 Amalgam; 267 Composite	Amalgam [See Bellinger 2006]	Composite resin [See Bellinger 2006]	Allocation: After completing baseline visits, children were randomized to a treatment arm: dental amalgam/ composite resin. Randomization was stratified by geographic location (Boston/Cambridge vs. Maine) and number of teeth with caries (2 to 4 vs. ≥ 5), with randomly permuted blocks within each of the four strata. Concealment: See Bellinger 2006	Patient: Psych
Bellinger 2007 [dose effect analysis][RCT] ¹⁷	534: 267 Amalgam; 267 Composite	Amalgam See Bellinger 2006	Composite resin See Bellinger 2006	See De Rouen 2006	Patient: DT, Exposure, NeuroPsych,
Barregard 2008 [RCT] ¹⁸	534: Amalgam n=267, Composite n=267	See Bellinger 2006	See Bellinger 2006	See Bellinger 2006	Patient: Renal

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De Rouen 2002;2006 [RCT] ¹⁹	507: 253 Amalgam; 254 Composite resin	Amalgam [Large posterior restorations]: Mercury content of different amalgams approximately same across different manufacturers (50%). Brand most widely used in USA (Dispersalloy, Dentsply). Treated with amalgam as appropriate in standard-of-care, but be treated with other materials (composite, glass ionomer, or compomer) if restorations not appropriate for amalgam	Composite resin: All DT met existing standards of care in USA/Portugal. Both groups: smaller+anterior restorations could be treated with other materials, selected from those typical of use in both countries. Most widely used composite USA: Z100 MP, 3M. Other materials used by dentists: composite adhesive, glass ionomer base, compomer and compomer adhesive, representative of what used in USA practice [Posterior composite Z100 MPq (3M), Composite adhesive Scotchbond multipurpose (3M), Glass ionomer base Vitrebond (3M), Compomer Dyract (Dentsply), Compomer adhesive Primabond 2.1 (Dentsply)]. Diagnoses dental disease/development treatment plans by lead dentist. Dental care providers trained to current standards of care in placing amalgam/composite restorations	Allocation: Stratification by 7 schools in system. Individual treatment appointments randomly assigned to providers. Concealment: Psychometrists+nerve conduction technicians instructed to not examine children intraorally (although adherence could not be guaranteed). Participants could not be blinded due to different appearance of materials	Patient: AE, Exposure, Neurological, Neurobehavioural, NeuroPsych, Renal
Lauterbach 2008 [RCT] ²⁰	507; 253 amalgam; 253 CRR ^b	Amalgam [See De Rouen 2006]	Composite resin [See De Rouen 2006]	See De Rouen 2006	Patient: Neurological
Roberts 2008 [Subset RCT] ²¹	150: 77 amalgam; 73 RBC	Amalgam [See De Rouen 2006]	Composite resin [See De Rouen 2006]	See De Rouen 2006	Patient: Exposure, GPH, OH

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Woods 2008 [RCT] ²²	507 original sample: NR; NR. Assume see De Rouen 2006	Amalgam [See De Rouen 2006]	Composite resin [See De Rouen 2006]	See De Rouen 2006	Patient: Renal
Martin 2008 [Prospective RCT] ²³	See De Rouen 2006	Amalgam [See De Rouen 2006]	Composite resin [See De Rouen 2006]	Allocation: See Bellinger 2006. Concealment: Children were assigned to one of two treatment groups (designated as Groups A and B or 1 and 2 to maintain blinding)	Patient: Renal
Geier 2011 [Secondary analysis RCT] ²⁴	See De Rouen 2007	Amalgam [See De Rouen 2006]	Composite resin [See De Rouen 2006]	See De Rouen 2006	Patient: Other - urinary porphyrins
Perng 2023 [Retrospective cohort with control] ²⁵	760, 379: 501,461 Caries group; 258,918 Non-caries group	In dental caries group: only resin restorations (n=180,127); amalgam + resin restorations (n=248, 936)	In dental caries group: amalgam restoration (n=72,398);	NA	Patient: IF
Amalgam removal and/or replacement					
Bjorkman 2012 [Pilot: Pre-post (health outcome)] ²⁶	40; 20; 20	Removal and replacement amalgam restorations: Patients had all amalgam restorations removed+replacement with other dental restorative materials. Treatment conducted by patients' dentists, following instructions from Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit (use rubber dam, high-volume suction, water cooling and to remove restorations in chunks using a sharp dental bur. Only a few amalgam restorations should be removed/session). Mean no.amalgam surfaces pre-treatment examination: 23.5 (SD 10.6)	Amalgam free group (blood donors)	NA	Patient: Exposure, IF

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Bjorkman 2017 [Prospective longitudinal with pre- post (control group results not included in this study)] ²⁷	20: NA; NA	Removal and replacement amalgam restorations in individuals with MUPS: replaced with other dental restorative materials by own dentists according to clinical guidelines aiming at minimal exposure to mercury during removal sessions. Majority new restorations polymer-based composites (79%). Other materials: Gold inlays, metaloceramic crowns, metalolo ceramic bridges, ceramic crowns, ceramic inlays, glass ionomer cements. Treatment group followed up at 3mnths, 1, 3 & 5yrs after amalgam removal	NA	Allocation: NA. Concealment: None [See Sjursen 2011]	Patient : AE, Exposure, GI, GPH, MSK, Neuropsych, OH, Psych,
Sjursen 2011 [Before and after with a comparison group] ²⁸	50: 20 treatment (+10 reserves); 20 control	Removal and replacement amalgam restorations: replaced with other dental restorative materials by own dentists according to clinical guidelines aiming at minimal exposure to mercury during removal sessions [54]: Amalgam restorations replaced with other dental restorative materials (e.g. composites, ceramic restorations and metaloceramic crowns). 18 dentists from 18 different dental practices: 1 dentist treated 3 patients; other dentists 1 patient each. Participants given written instructions to contact Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit if experienced increased health complaints e.g. chills, fever, pain and rashes in relation to amalgam replacement process. Instructions included advice to patient's physician regarding blood tests to be taken (leucocytes, CRP, IgE and mercury concentration in blood) in case of increased health complaints after DT.	No intervention. Both groups followed up at 3mnths, 1, 3 & 5yrs	Allocation: Randomly allocated. Concealment: Dentists: Replacement of amalgam restorations not possible to mask: no blinding used	Patient : AE, Exposure, GPH, Orofacial

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Frisk 2007 [Controlled Before and After] ²⁹	46; 24; 22	<p>Removal of dental materials (predominantly amalgam) in individuals with health problems attributed to amalgam: After medical examination, patients recommended removal of incriminated dental materials. Dental amalgam most common dental material, followed by different gold alloys and non-precious metal alloys. DT aim: remove all manageable amounts of these materials, detectable by dental investigation methods, e.g., x-rays. Protocol for restoration with individually compatible materials implemented.</p> <p>Adequate equipment in working premises, e.g., catalytic mercury vapor traps and high-volume suction-capacity equipment mandatory. Instructions for specified burs, diamond bits, or ultra-sonic bits for each metal restoration+instructions for different barriers between patients' teeth and adjacent tissues in oral cavity. Each patient received standard regimen of antioxidants orally [see Sjursen 2011]</p>	Assume no intervention	NA	Patient: Clinical chemistry variables, Exposure, IF
Geier 2013 [Subset RCT] ³⁰	NR	Amalgam [See De Rouen 2006]	Composite resin [See De Rouen 2006]	NR	Patient: Renal

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Lartitegui-Sebastian 2012 [Prospective clinical observational study with pre-post design] ³¹	100: 7 with OLL; 93 without OLL	Removal & replacement amalgam: Individuals with OLL with min.1 silver amalgam. Amalgams replaced with composite and monitored at 3 & 6mths	Individuals without OLL with min.1 silver amalgam	NA	Patient: Allergy, OH
Lynch 2015 [Retrospective cohort with before and after element] ³²	31; 14 patients had their amalgam removed (8 positive Hg reaction, 6 negative Hg reaction); 17 no amalgam removal (15 negative Hg reaction, 2 positive Hg reaction)	Patients with OLL who had partial/complete replacement of amalgams	No amalgams removed/replaced	NA	Patient: Allergy, OH
Marell 2014 [Retrospective cohort with before and after component] ³³	44; 39 had restorations replaced (23 complete replacement, 16 partial replacement); 5 didn't have restorations replaced	Replacement or partial replacement of dental restorations among individuals with OLP or LCR. Most frequently replaced material: dental amalgam. Choice of replacement materials often mixture of materials, e.g. metal ceramic crowns in noble alloys in molar region, composite or glass-ionomer in canines and premolars	No replacement of dental restorations among individuals with OLP or LCR	NA	Patient: Allergy, OH

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Melchart 2008 [RCT] ³⁴	90: 30 removal group; 39 removal + biol. detoxification; 31 no- removal ^c	Removal and replacement amalgam restorations: Amalgam removed by quadrant min. 1wk between visits; underlying restorations/carious dentin removed. Calcium hydroxide as liner for very deep restorations (caries profunda) before restoration with ceramic or gold inlays, or composite restoration	1) Removal-plus: participants also treated with high doses of vitamins and trace elements (following recommendations International Association for Holistic Dental Medicine), intended to support excretion of mercury from body. Biological detoxification therapy lasted 12wks, beginning 4wks before amalgam removal-daily tablets containing: vitamin B6 (100 mg), vitamin C (1 g), vitamin E (300 mg), calcium (500 mg), selenium (200 µg as sodium selenite), zinc orotate (2 x 40 mg, i.e., 2 x 6.3 mg zinc), and garlic preparation (1 x 100-300 mg). Participants not allowed to take vitamin C+selenium at same time of day. 2) No removal of amalgam restorations: health promotion program to develop health-related lifestyle management skills suitable for individuals' everyday life . 14x2hr group sessions (max.12 participants), conducted by professionals from Centre for Complementary Medicine Research	Allocation: Randomization by telephone according to random list generated in advance, stratified according to no. amalgam restoration surfaces. Concealment: Participants not blinded to treatment	Patient: AE, Exposure, GPH, Psych, SAE

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Montebugnoli 2012 [Before and after] ³⁵	64: 64 (25 OLL patients and 39 OLP patients); NA	Replacement of amalgam restorations with composite resin	NA	NA	Patient: OH
Naimi-Akbar 2013 [CBA] ³⁶	174: Replacement group: 161, non-replacement group=13	Restoration removal: dental amalgam replaced in 211 patients (90.6%). Other dental materials replaced: gold alloys (79 subjects; 33.9%), composite (48 subjects; 20.6%), ceramics (35 subjects; 15%), titanium (20subjects; 8.6%), acrylics in dentures (19 subjects;8.2%), metals in dentures (10 subjects; 4.3%) and cobalt-chromium alloys (eight subjects; 3.4%)	NA	NA	Patient: GPH, IF, MSK, OH, Other, Psych,
Pezelj-Ribaric 2008 [Retrospective cohort] ³⁷	40: 20; 20	Amalgam restoration replacement for individuals with OLR. Complete replacement of all amalgam restorations with restorations based on composite resin, gold, porcelain or combination of these	Healthy controls with no OLR	NA	Patient: Allergy, IF, OH
Sinha 2024 [Prospective cohort (with control groups)] ³⁸	85: 37 Symptoms attributed to amalgam; 33 MUPS not attributed to amalgam; 25 Healthy cohort OR Amalgam (Response at Q3 follow up: 32; 28; 19)	Removal of amalgam restorations in Amalgam cohort	Amalgam not replaced in comparison groups (MUPS (patients with medically unexplained physical symptoms not attributed to amalgam restorations) and healthy cohorts)	NA	Patient: Allergy, Anthromorphic, Auditory, CVD, Dermatological, ENT, FH, GI, GPH, MSK, NeuroPsych, OH, Orofacial, Psych, Resp, Visual/Ocular
Weidenhammer 2010 [Secondary analysis RCT] ³⁹	90 vs 55 vs 23	Removal of amalgam restorations in Amalgam cohort	Non removal of amalgam [Health promoting program]	Allocation: Post hoc analysis of randomized trial. Concealment: NR	Patient: Exposure, GPH, Psych

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Zwicker 2014 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ⁴⁰	955: 250 Treatment group (amalgam restorations removed); 167 Positive Amalgam group; 538 Never Amalgam group	Presence of amalgam restorations: All participants with amalgam restorations offered opportunity to have amalgam restorations removed by dental team and dental restoration, with precaution to minimize exposure to mercury vapor and amalgam particles. Dental benefits and risks discussed during initial consultation. Treatment group: amalgam restorations completely removed. Positive amalgam group: positive number amalgam surfaces throughout study period+ second urine mercury measure min. six months after 1st measure	Never amalgam group: Never had amalgam restorations	NA	Patient: ENT, Exposure, GI, GPH, MSK, Neurological, Neuropsych, Psych
Lygre 2013 [CBA] ⁴¹	20: 19 Amalgam; 441 Reference	Removal of amalgam restorations and replacement with other restorative materials	External reference group (general population)	NA	Patient: CVD, Dermatological, ENT, GI, GPH, MSK, NeuroPsych, Orofacial, Psych, Visual Ocular
Bjorkman 2023 [Prospective longitudinal] ⁴²	66: 20 Amalgam cohort; 25 MUPS cohort; 11 Healthy cohort	Removal amalgam restorations and replacement with other restorative materials: carried out by patient's dentist. 32 patients with medically unexplained symptoms attributed to amalgam (Amalgam cohort) given DT at 212 sessions within project. Mean no. treatment sessions: 6.6 (median 6.5, range 2 to 13). Dental amalgam restorations removed in total of 179 treatment sessions (dentist documentation) or 178 sessions (patient documentation). Rubber dam used in about three-quarter removal sessions, water-cooling and high-volume evacuation according to dentist/patient documentation used in 94% and 92%, respectively. Rubber dam, water-	No dental amalgam removal in individuals with MUPS not attributed to amalgam (MUPS) and Healthy cohorts	Allocation: See Bjorkman 2020. Concealment: NR	Patient: AE, Exposure, GPH, SAE

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		cooling and high-volume evacuation not used in all amalgam removal sessions for 17 patients (dentist documentation)			
Bjorkman 2020 [Prospective longitudinal with pre- post and control] ⁴³	79: 32 Amalgam cohort; 28 MUPS cohort; 19 Healthy cohort	Removal amalgam restorations and replacement with other restorative materials.	MUPS/Healthy	Allocation: Amalgam cohort. After application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 1) and after having returned the signed informed consent, the patient was included in the study (Figure 2). MUPS Cohort. After a regular consultation of the GP, patients who fulfilled criteria were given an envelope with written information about the study. Patients who were interested to participate in the study (labelled as “Changes of health complaints over time”) signed the written informed consent and sent it to the study office. Healthy cohort: After returning the signed written informed consent, Questionnaire 1 (Q1; baseline) was mailed to	Patient: GPH, Psych

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				the participants. Concealment: NR	
Suter 2016 [Retrospective observational case control (health outcome)] ⁴⁴	115 Patch test positive: 78 to dental materials; 13 to non- dental contactants; 24 Patch test negative. 87 total at follow up: 32 Amalgam removed (26 positive patch test amalgam-related allergen, 6 negative patch test to amalgam allergen); 51 No amalgam replaced (15 positive patch test amalgam-related allergen, 36 negative patch test amalgam allergen n=36)	Replacement of amalgam restoration with other materials for those with positive patch test:allergen material discussed with patient. 5 patch-negative patients required replacement of restoration/dental extraction to restore dental health. Amalgam-related allergens: ammoniated mercury (1%), amalgam (5%), amalgam alloying metal (20%), nickel sulphate (5%). 98 patients (85.2%) had min.1 amalgam restorations, with at least one of these in direct contact with mucosal reaction(s)	Amalgam not replaced	NA	Patient: Allergy, OH

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Amalgam in situ					
Adams 2008 [Case control] ⁴⁵	109 (78 autism group, 31 Neurotypical control group)	Exposure: Received amalgam restoration. Mean N (SD) Maternal Hg restorations: 5.5(4.2) Autism group; 6.6(3.6) control group. Mean (SD) Maternal Hg restorations placed during pregnancy: 4% autism group, 3% control group	NA	NA	Child-Maternal exposure: Autism, Exposure
Bjorkman 2018 [Prospective longitudinal] ⁴⁶	72038: 56339 Amalgam; 15699 No amalgam	Exposure: Teeth filled with dental amalgam	No Amalgam restorations	NA	Patient: Pregnancy outcomes
Cabana-Munoz 2015 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁴⁷	55: 42 Amalgam; 13 No amalgam	Exposure: Amalgam restorations min. 10yrs. Women divided 2 groups: <4 dental amalgam restorations (n= 27); >4 amalgam restorations; (n=15)	No amalgam restorations	NA	Patient: Oxidative stress
Cabana-Munoz 2019 [Cross sectional with control] ⁴⁸	130: 54 long-term titanium dental implants and amalgams; 51 patients long-term dental amalgam alone; 25 controls no dental materials	Exposure: Group 1) Amalgam + long term titanium implants; 2) Amalgam alone	No dental materials	NA	Patient: Exposure, Other-taurine/Oxidative stress
Chen 2020 [Retrospective observational: Case control] ⁴⁹	11,424: 5712 Amalgam; 5712 No amalgam	Exposure: Received amalgam restoration	No Amalgam restorations	NA	Patient: Neurological

Study [SD]	Total Patient N: Patients receiving intervention (N); Patients receiving control treatment (N)	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Comparator (description)	Allocation procedure: Concealment attempts	Population: Broad outcome category/ies evaluated
Chen 2021 [Retrospective observational: Case control] ⁵⁰	11,696: 6606 Amalgam; 5090 No amalgam	Exposure: Received amalgam restoration	No Amalgam restorations	NA	Patient: IF
Daniel 2007 [Prospective cohort] ⁵¹	7375: NA; NA	Exposure: Amalgam restoration, either before or during pregnancy	NA	NA	Patient: Exposure, NeuroPsych, Pregnancy outcomes
Duplinsky 2012 [Cohort with control group] ⁵²	396 Dentists	Exposure: Amalgam	NA	NA	Dental professional: CVD, GPH, Neurological, NeuroPsych, Psych, Resp
Eyeson 2010 [Retrospective record review] ⁵³	62: 56 Patients; 6 controls	Exposure: Amalgam restoration	No amalgam restorations	NA	Patient: Allergy, CVD, Exposure, GPH, IF, MSK, Neurological, OH, Psych
Franzblau 2012 [Cross- sectional/longitudinal] ⁵⁴	2767 study participants (3771 observations over 10yrs). 3594 observations from 2656 subjects available for analyses, including those with imputed body mass index (BMI); NA	Exposure: No. amalgam restorations placed and removed/wk	NA	NA	Dental professional: Exposure, Neurological

Study [SD]	Total Patient N: Patients receiving intervention (N); Patients receiving control treatment (N)	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Comparator (description)	Allocation procedure: Concealment attempts	Population: Broad outcome category/ies evaluated
Heggland 2011 [Retrospective cohort (records review)] ⁵⁵	113,0251: 5493 Dental professionals with exposure mercury vapour; 112,4758 controls with no mercury vapour exposure	Exposure: Amalgam/Hg vapour	General population: No mercury vapour exposure	NA	Dental professional: Pregnancy outcomes
Hilt 2009 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁵⁶	1033: 608 DA; 425 Controls	Assume Amalgam: Exposure metallic mercury	No exposure metallic mercury	NA	Dental professional: Exposure, GPH, Neurological, NeuroPsych, Psych
Hilt 2011 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁵⁷	623: 406 Dentists; 217 Controls	Copper amalgam: Exposure to mercury	No exposure to occupational mercury	NA	Dental professional: Exposure, GPH, Neurological, NeuroPsych, Psych
Hsu 2016 [Retrospective cohort] ⁵⁸	20740; 10, 236 Amalgam; 10, 236 No amalgam	Exposure: Min.1 amalgam restoration	No amalgam restorations	NA	Patient: Neurological

Study [SD]	Total Patient N: Patients receiving intervention (N); Patients receiving control treatment (N)	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Comparator (description)	Allocation procedure: Concealment attempts	Population: Broad outcome category/ies evaluated
Jones 2007 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁵⁹	75: 43 Exposed; 32 matched controls	Copper amalgam-mercury exposure	No Hg exposure	NA	Dental professional: Dermatological Endocrine FH GPH MSK NeuroPsych Pregnancy outcomes Psych
Louopou 2020 [Prospective cohort] ⁶⁰	2001: 2001; NA	Exposure: Mercury-silver restorations. Women asked 1) quantity mercury-silver dental restorations, 2) how many had replaced. Question 2 repeated third trimester visit. Specific composition dental amalgams not available	NA	NA	Patient: Exposure, Maternal Health
Lygre 2018 [Prospective cohort] ⁶¹	69652 children	Maternal exposure amalgam during pregnancy: restoration or removal	NA	NA	Child - Maternal exposure: ADHD
Lygre 2016 [Prospective cohort] ⁶²	69 474 pregnancies	Maternal exposure amalgam during pregnancy: restoration or removal	NA	NA	Child - Maternal exposure: Pregnancy outcomes

Study [SD]	Total Patient N: Patients receiving intervention (N); Patients receiving control treatment (N)	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Comparator (description)	Allocation procedure: Concealment attempts	Population: Broad outcome category/ies evaluated
Thygesen 2011 [Retrospective Observational: Cohort Study] ⁶³	122 481 persons included. Exposed vs non-occupationally exposed	Occupational mercury exposure via amalgam	NA	NA	Dental professional: Neurological, Renal, SAE
Tseng 2020a [Retrospective observational: case- control study] ⁶⁴	1224: 757 Amalgam; 467 No amalgam	Exposure: Presence of amalgam restorations	No Amalgam restoration	NA	Patient: Neurological
Tseng 2020b [Retrospective observational: case- control study] ⁶⁵	6016: 3039 Amalgam; 2977 No amalgam	Exposure: Presence of amalgam restorations	No Amalgam restoration	NA	Patient: Neurological
Sundstrom 2010 [Longitudinal and cross- sectional with control group] ⁶⁶	684: 342 Health complaints attributed to amalgam; 342 Controls. Longitudinal data: 81 participants with amalgam related complaints	Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam restorations	Control group: One-to-one matched control individuals. no health complaints attributed to amalgam restorations	NA	Patient: CVD, Dermatological, ENT, GI, GPH, MSK, NeuroPsych, Psych, Resp, Urinary, Visual/Ocular

Study [SD]	Total Patient N: Patients receiving intervention (N); Patients receiving control treatment (N)	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Comparator (description)	Allocation procedure: Concealment attempts	Population: Broad outcome category/ies evaluated
Sundstrom 2011 [Longitudinal and cross-sectional with control group] ⁶⁷	674: 337 Health complaints attributed to amalgam; 337 Controls	Case group: Presence of health complaints attributed to amalgam restorations	Control group: No health complaints attributed to amalgam restorations	NA	Patient: CVD, Dermatological, ENT, GI, GPH, MSK, Psych, Resp, Urinary, Visual/Ocular
Watson 2011 [Prospective longitudinal cohort study] ⁶⁸	587: NA; NA	Exposure: Presence of amalgam restorations	NA	NA	Maternal exposure: Exposure, NeuroPsych
Watson 2012 [Prospective longitudinal cohort study] ⁶⁹	242: NA; NA	Exposure: Presence of amalgam restorations	NA	NA	Maternal exposure: Exposure, NeuroPsych
Watson 2013 [Prospective longitudinal cohort study] ⁷⁰	236: NA; NA	Exposure: Presence of amalgam restorations	NA	NA	Patients: Exposure, NeuroPsych
Weber 2012 [Prospective longitudinal with control] ⁷¹	113: 65 Oral squamous cell carcinoma ; 48 Control	Exposure: Patch testing 28 metal allergens commonly used in dental repairs including amalgam/mercury. Participants diagnosed/history with oral squamous cell carcinoma	Control patients with no history oral disease: patch tested 8 common metals (various forms of gold, silver, copper, and mercury)	NR	Patient: Allergy/Cancer (oral)

Study [SD]	Total Patient N: Patients receiving intervention (N); Patients receiving control treatment (N)	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Comparator (description)	Allocation procedure: Concealment attempts	Population: Broad outcome category/ies evaluated
Weidenhammer 2009 [Retrospective data analysis- (sample 1 retrospective data analysis of RCT and sample 2 historical records)] ⁷²	206: 90; 116	Symptoms attributed to presence of amalgam restorations	Patients attributing complaints to environmental chemicals e.g. solvents, pesticides, or timber preservatives, not mercury from dental restorations	NA	Patient: Dermatological, GI, GPH, MSK, OH, Neuropsych, Psych
Wright 2012 [Case control] ⁷³	251: 54 children on autism spectrum; 155 children without autism; 42 children siblings of those with ASD	Exposure: Presence of amalgam restorations/ Mercury in urine and autism	Presence of amalgam restorations/ Mercury in urine and no autism	Allocation: NA. Concealment: Urine samples blinded with code numbers and delivered via one of several points of collection to local Department of Clinical Biochemistry within 24 hours. Analytical laboratories remained blinded to identity/diagnosis throughout	Patient: Autism
Naimi-Akbar 2012 [Retrospective cohort with control] ⁷⁴	13045: 3546 Exposed (365 sons female dentists+3181 sons dental nurses); 13045 Unexposed (378 sons female physicians+ 12667 assistant nurses)	Occupational exposure to amalgam	Non-amalgam exposure via occupation	NA	Maternal exposure (health prof): NeuroPsych

Study [SD]	Total Patient N: Patients receiving intervention (N); Patients receiving control treatment (N)	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Comparator (description)	Allocation procedure: Concealment attempts	Population: Broad outcome category/ies evaluated
Naimi-Akbar 2014 [Retrospective cohort with control] ⁷⁵	59700: 12110 Exposed (10420 dental nurses+1690 dentists); 47591 Unexposed (44908 assistant nurse+2683 physicians)	Occupational exposure to amalgam	Non-amalgam exposure via occupation	NA	Maternal exposure (health prof): Pregnancy outcomes
Piagno 2020 [Modelling] ⁷⁶	NA	Exposure: Amalgam emissions from crematorium	NA	NA	Exposure
Ahlgren 2014 [Case control] ⁷⁷	74(89 %) patients in OLL group; 73 (88 %) patients in DP group had amalgam restorations. 42/74 composite restorations adjacent to lichen lesions	OLL group: Exposure: Amalgam or composite restoration	DP group: Exposure: Amalgam or composite restoration	NR	Patient : Allergy, OH
Halperin-Sternfeld 2016 [Retrospective cohort (records review)] ⁷⁸	50: T0: 1301 teeth assessed; 721 Unrestored teeth; 580 Restored teeth (225 amalgam restorations, 93 Composite) ^d	Exposure: Amalgam or composite restoration	NA	NA	Patient: DT, OH

Study [SD]	Total Patient N: Patients receiving intervention (N); Patients receiving control treatment (N)	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Comparator (description)	Allocation procedure: Concealment attempts	Population: Broad outcome category/ies evaluated
Ma 2021 [Retrospective observational: nested case-control] ⁷⁹	2105: 421 (patients with OLP); 1,684 (propensity score matched controls- no OLP)	Exposure: Presence of amalgam restorations/composite resin restorations and OLP	Exposure: Presence of amalgam/composite restorations in people without OLP	NA	Patient: OH
Ptak 2023 [Retrospective cohort] ⁸⁰	2177: 628 Amalgam; 1151 Composite ^e	Exposure: Amalgam/composite restoration	NA	NA	Patient: OH
Daume 2021 [Cross- sectional with control group] ⁸¹	112; Compsite 95, Amalgam 55, ceramic 81, gold 47, non- precious metal 69	Individuals with reticular OLP. Exposure: Amalgam, composite, ceramic, gold, non- previous metal	Individuals with non-reticular OLP exposed to materials of interest	NR	Patient: OH
Mikhailichenko 2019 [Retrospective observational: Nested case-control] ⁸²	Diagnosed dementia: 16 666 vs Never diagnosed dementia (control group)-age- sex matched controls: 33,332	Dementia group: Exposure: amalgam/CRR	Non-dementia group: Exposure: amalgam/CRR	NA	Patient: NeuroPsych

Study [SD]	Total Patient N: Patients receiving intervention (N); Patients receiving control treatment (N)	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Comparator (description)	Allocation procedure: Concealment attempts	Population: Broad outcome category/ies evaluated
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 [Cross sectional with control group] ⁸³	80; 40 atopic subjects; 40 non-atopic subjects	Exposure to dental materials. Of interest: amalgam and methacrylates (atopic subjects)	Exposure to dental materials. Of interest: amalgam and methacrylates (non-atopic subjects)	NA	Patient: Allergy, OH
Forkel 2024 [Retrospective record review] ⁸⁴	2730 included in analyses	Exposure: Dental prostheses, restorations or implants considered problematic materials. Of relevance: methacrylates, amalgam [restorations]	NR	NA	Patient: Allergy
Heratizadeh 2018 [Retrospective case control] ⁸⁵	163 261 patients were patch tested, 399 DT (226 OCD, 142 No OCD)	OCD group: Testing for allergy to methacrylates/acrylates and amalgam/amalgam metals	Non-OCD group: Testing for allergy to methacrylates/acrylates and amalgam/amalgam metals	NA	Dental professionals: Allergy
Multiple					
Lin 2017 [Retrospective cohort] ⁸⁶	44034 amalgam; 44034 other restorations	Amalgam	Other types of restoration: including resin composite, glass ionomer	NA	Patient: ADHD

Study [SD]	Total Patient N: Patients receiving intervention (N); Patients receiving control treatment (N)	Intervention or Exposure of interest (description)	Comparator (description)	Allocation procedure: Concealment attempts	Population: Broad outcome category/ies evaluated
Lindbohm 2007 [Retrospective/cross-sectional with control group] ⁸⁷	720: 222 cases (Women experience miscarriage); 498 controls (Women with successful births)	Exposure: Dental restorative materials containing acrylate compounds, mercury amalgam. Of interest to review: Exposure HEMA: Frequency restoration cementation/replacement composite resin or glass ionomer restoration. Exposure TEGDMA: No. removed CRR/wk. Exposure Hg Amalgam: No. amalgam or composite restorations made/removed per wk; using mercury amalgam before pregnancy; no. removed composite resin restorations/wk. Exposure MMA: as low (air concentration ,1 ppm) for all dentists and dental nurses/hygienists, as well as for all dental technicians and laboratory workers who handled the raw materials of acrylic resins/plastics or worked in the room where they were handled for not more than 2 h a week. Dental technicians and dental laboratory workers who worked for .2 h/week with these materials belonged to the high category (1–20 ppm). Exposure PMMA: All the women who used protective equipment when grinding acrylate products or worked in same room for 7 h/week+those working in dental offices classified exposed to organic PMMA dust.	No exposure of interest	Allocation: NA. Concealment: The assessment was conducted blinded to the participant's case-control status	Dental professionals: Pregnancy outcomes
<p>aAmalgam: 1 Received Composite (Refused Amalgam) 4 Chose Not to Receive Restorations, Composite: 2 Received Amalgam 2 Chose Not to Receive Restorations, bData from the neurological examination are missing for one subject in the resin-based composite group. cITT population. Statistical testing of the main outcome measure was performed on the ITT population. d282 Fixed partial dentures. eCrown restorations (n = 398) make up the remainder. AD=Alzheimer's Disease, ADHD=Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, AE=Adverse Events, ASD=Autistic Spectrum Disorder, CBA=Controlled Before and After, CRP=, CRR=Composite Resin Restoration, CTG=Connective Tissue Graft, CVD=Cardiovascular Disease, DA=Dental Amalgam,DAs=Dental Assistants, DP=Dermatitis Patients, DT=Dental Treatment, ENT=Ear/Nose/Throat, FH=Female Health, GI=Gastrointestinal, GIC=Glass Ionomer Cement, GPH=General Physical Health, hr=Hour, IF=Immune Function, LCR=Lichenoid Contact Reaction, MSK=Musculo-skeletal, MUPS=Medically Unexplained Physical Symptoms, n/N=Number, NA=Not Applicable, Neuropsych=Neuropsychological, NR=Not Reported, OCD=Occupational Contact Dermatitis, OH=Oral Health, OF=Orofacial, OLL=Oral Lichenoid Lesions, OLP=Oral Lichen Planus,PRR=Preventative Resin Restoration, Psych=Psychosocial, RCT=Randomized Controlled Trial, Resp=Respiratory, SAE=Serious Adverse Events,TEGDMA=Triethylene Glycol Dimethacrylate, USA=United States of America, wks=Weeks, yrs=Years</p>					

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